

Rare cause of hypochromicmicrocytic anaemia

Jasmine Christie¹, Adel Ekladios²

1.Department of Medicine, Royal Darwin Hospital, Darwin, NT,

2Department of Medicine, Bunbury Hospital, Bunbury, WA.

Correspondence to: Adel Ekladios, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, The University of Western Australia, 35 Stirling Highway, Perth, Australia, 6009

Received: 18 July 2021; Accepted: 27 July 2021

Citation: Jasmine Christie, Adel Ekladios. Rare cause of hypochromicmicrocytic anaemia. IJDMS. 2021; 2(2): 1-3.

ABSTRACT

A 35-year-old lady who had persistent iron deficiency anaemia underwent extensive investigations over the course of six months with involvement of seven different medicalspecialties before a diagnosis of pica disorder causing lead poisoning was formally made. The patient eventually received chelation therapy and made a full recovery. More targeted history taking could have assisted in making an earlier diagnosis.

Keywords: iron deficiency, anaemia, pica disorder, lead poisoning

A 35-year-old lady of Asian descent presented to the emergency department with lower abdominal pain, fatigue and exhaustion. She has no significant past medical or surgical history and denied taking any regular prescription or over-the-counter medication. She described having menorrhagia, denied any constitutional symptoms, had no infective symptoms, and had a normal balanced diet. On physical examination, all of her vital signs were within normal limits, and cardiorespiratory, abdominal and thyroid examination were unremarkable. It was noted that she looked pale and had brittle and spoon-shaped nails (koilonychia). A spot pregnancy test was negative. Basic blood showed microcytic anaemia (Hb 70 g/L, MCV 89 fL) and peripheral blood film showed basophilic stippling. Iron studies were completed and revealed the following: serum iron <2 umol/L (reference value: 10.0-30.0 umol/L), transferrin 0.8g/L (reference value: 2.10-3.80 g/L), transferrin saturation 10% (reference value: 15-45%), and ferritin 8ug/L (reference value: 30-120 ug/L)⁶. In light of the examination and blood findings consistent with iron deficiency anaemia, the patient was admitted under the general medicine team and received an iron infusion. Gynaecology advice was obtained due to her menorrhagia as a potential cause of her anaemia. A recommended abdominal ultrasound was completed and showed uterine fibroids. She was started on the combined oral contraceptive pill

and was booked for a hysteroscopy as an out-patient. She was discharged the following day with planned gynaecology and gastroenterology follow up.

On routine follow up with her general practitioner (GP), she still described ongoing exhaustion and decreased exercise tolerance. Her repeat blood tests showed ongoing microcytic anaemia (Hb 100 g/L, MCV 96 fL). She was started on oral iron tablets, however, this caused nausea and constipation, and was resultantly ceased. She was given a second iron transfusion with no resolution of her symptoms. On outpatient review with gastroenterology, coeliac screen was negative, and she underwent a gastroscopy and colonoscopy. Biopsies taken from gastroscopy confirmed *Helicobacter pylori*, and she was treated with eradication therapy. Several weeks later, she was re-admitted under neurology due to a generalised tonic-clonic seizure that was treated with levetiracetam. Electroencephalogram (EEG) did not show any signs consistent with epilepsy, but rather diffuse slowing of the normal background frequency consistent with encephalopathy. Hepatic, Wernicke's and uremic encephalopathy were ruled out and levetiracetam was ceased. Basic bloods confirmed

persistent microcytic anaemia (Hb 69 g/L, MCV 80 fL). She was transfused two units of packed red blood cells and had a third iron transfusion. She remained an inpatient and was referred to the gastroenterology team. Calprotectin, faecal occult blood test, repeat coeliac screen, capsule endoscopy, push endoscopy, and magnetic resonance imaging of the abdomen and pelvis were all negative. She was also re-referred to the gynaecology team who were strongly convinced it was not directly related to her menorrhagia or fibroids. Thyroid function test's (TFT) showed a mildly elevated thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) and normal T3 and T4, consistent with subclinical hypothyroidism. She was then referred to the endocrinology team who completed thyroid antibodies including thyroid peroxidase, anti-thyroglobulin, and thyroid receptor antibodies which were weakly positive. She was started on 25 micrograms of levothyroxine and discharged home.

On follow up with her GP, repeat TFT's showed an elevated T4 and she was in atrial fibrillation. Levothyroxine was subsequently ceased, and she was referred for a transthoracic echocardiogram (TTE) which was negative. She remained persistently iron deficient and was iron transfused again for the fourth time. Additional red blood cell nuclear scan and computed tomography (CT) angiogram were performed and were negative. Her symptoms and blood investigations remained unchanged and she received her fifth iron transfusion. She had numerous trips to the ED with abdominal pain flare ups and constipation. Her mental health deteriorated, and she was referred to a psychiatrist who diagnosed her with anxiety and major depressive disorder, and she was started on escitalopram. She received a further two iron transfusions – a total of seven iron transfusions received in 6 months. Lastly, she was referred to a haematologist who offered a bone marrow biopsy which she declined. Further extensive blood investigations including a panel of heavy metals showed an elevated lead level of 1000 mcg/dL and free erythrocyte protoporphyrin level of 300 mcg/dL. Basophilic stippling was still evident on peripheral blood smear. She was admitted to hospital and commenced on succimer chelation therapy.

More extensive history taking eventually revealed she had pica disorder that was not picked up previously. A home visit was arranged by the occupational therapist and revealed large areas of her walls where paint had been chipped off and being eaten. Lead level in the paint were elevated and was also detected in the patient's imported spices and herbs that she was using regularly in her cooking. In a matter of days, her symptoms significantly improved, and it was the first time she had felt like her normal self again. The escitalopram was ceased, and repeat blood tests were finally normal. She was no longer anaemic (Hb 140 g/L, MCV 90 fL) and iron studies were normalised (serum iron 33 umol/L, transferrin 3.0 g/L, transferrin saturation 40%, and ferritin 100 ug/L). The patient underwent behavioural intervention and nutritional rehabilitation for her pica disorder, and she was discharged back to the GP without any further admissions to the ED. A few months later, she underwent a hysterectomy for her uterine fibroids.

Discussion:

Pica is an unusual condition whereby patients develop non-nutritive cravings of edible or inedible substance which can pose significant health risk. This includes electrolyte and metabolic disorders, lead and mercury poisonings, parasitic infections, tooth wear, and intestinal obstruction. Pica has been shown to be associated with iron deficiency anaemia as demonstrated in the case above. No safe levels of lead have been established and avoidance of exposure should be heavily encouraged.² Although Australia has generally low levels of environmental lead, elevated levels can still be found in and around some mining towns, and within manufacturing industries that process batteries, ammunition, pigments, solder, and radiators.³ Therefore, discussing the patient's occupation, hobbies, social and psychiatric history is imperative in assisting in diagnosis. The neurological system is the most sensitive system affected by lead poisoning and can present with polyneuropathy, encephalopathy, delirium, ataxia, seizures, and coma. Other clinical features include severe abdominal pain, constipation, arthralgias, myalgias, and purple-blue gum line (also known as 'Burton lines'). Toxic renal manifestations of chronic lead poisoning include acute gouty arthritis secondary to hyperuricaemia, and proximal tubular acidosis causing phosphaturia, aminoaciduria and glycosuria, uricosuria, and calciuria.

Lead poisoning diagnosis can be made by the following: microcytic and hypochromic anaemia, elevated blood lead levels and basophilic stippling of erythrocytes on peripheral blood smear. Other basophilic stippling differentials include iron deficiency anaemia, megaloblastic anaemia (due to B12, folate, and copper deficiency), thalassaemia, liver disease, unstable haemoglobin disease, and nucleotidase deficiency. Moreover, a diagnosis of lead poisoning should not be made on peripheral blood smear alone but rather in conjunction with other investigations. Blood lead levels do not reflect the total amount stored in the body as 94% of lead is stored in the cortical bones and transfers to the blood during iron, calcium or zinc deficiency, and pregnancy.⁵ Although imaging is not routinely indicated in lead poisoning, lead flecks may be seen on abdominal x-ray and lead lines may be seen on long bone x-rays.¹

Lead poisoning treatment consists of chelation therapy in patients who are symptomatic or with high blood lead concentrations (above 70-80 ug/dL in adults and above 50ug/dL in children).⁴ Most patients can be managed as an outpatient on oral chelation therapy, however, patients with lead encephalopathy need to be admitted for parenteral chelation therapy. As per the Therapeutic Guidelines, oral 2,3-dimercaptosuccinic acid (DMSA, Succimer) 10mg/kg orally is used 8-hourly for 5 days, followed by 10mg/kg every 12-hourly for 14 days. Parenteral chelation therapy used for patients with lead encephalopathy consists of dimercaptopropane-1-sulfonate (DMPS) 5mg/kg intravenously every 6-hours for 5 days. Once oral chelation therapy is appropriate, intravenous therapy can be switched to oral for at least 14 days after parenteral therapy. Blood lead levels need weekly monitoring during therapy and 14 days after therapy to check for lead redistribution from bone. In addition, iron, zinc and copper levels should be checked prior to and during chelation therapy as there is a risk of micronutrient deficiency. ¹ Once lead poisoning has been treated in pica disorder, a home visit should be organised by the multi-disciplinary team to inspect the environment for any other potential lead sources. Moreover, exploring long-term strategies to assist with pica disorder in the form of cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT)

will assist in building ongoing skills around distinguishing edible foods from non-edible ones. In conclusion, invasive and expensive investigations could have been limited and definitive diagnosis could have been made earlier if a patient with a history of pica disorder with changes in behaviour, seizure with no epileptogenic focus, non-responsiveness to iron infusions and depression with commencement of antidepressant were identified as red flags for uncommon causes of iron deficiency anaemia such as lead poisoning.

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